

Childhood Bullying Victimization and Mental Health Outcomes in College Students: A Review of Long-term Effects and Coping Processes

Navanitha M. and Annalakshmi N.

Department of Psychology, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu

Bullying victimization is a prevalent developmental stressor and is repeatedly linked with negative psychological consequences and with effects that may persist into emerging adulthood. This review aims to synthesize evidence on mental health outcomes and key coping processes among college students with a history of childhood bullying. The present review includes the literature on long-term mental health outcomes of bullying victimization in childhood, taken from electronic databases like PubMed, APA PsycArticles, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, JSTOR, using a combination of key terms related to childhood bullying victimization and mental health outcomes. Search terms included “bullying” OR “school bullying” OR “peer victimization” OR “victims of bullying” AND “childhood trauma” OR “mental health” OR “psychological distress” OR “self-esteem” OR “emotion regulation” OR “distress tolerance” OR “resilience” OR “forgiveness” OR “emerging adulthood” OR “college students”. Relevant national and international studies were examined and synthesized. Studies reveal consistent associations with increased emotional distress and deficits in psychological and social adjustment. A limited understanding persists of how psychological difficulties following bullying develop across the lifespan or interact with a person's coping resources and contextual supports. Overall, this review also highlights the importance of integrating interventions at the college level that help to recover from the impact of childhood bullying. The review concludes by emphasizing the need for contextually sensitive, trauma-informed approaches within campus mental health systems to better support this vulnerable student population.

Keywords: Bullying, mental health, emerging adulthood, college students

Bullying victimization includes ongoing abuse between persons of similar age, where there is a power imbalance that interrupts the victims from defending themselves (Olweus, 1993; 2013). Childhood bullying involvement, primarily as a victim or bully-victim, is strongly linked with negative outcomes in adulthood, such as reduced physical and mental health, lower economic stability, and poor social relationships, even after accounting for early family problems and childhood psychiatric problems (Wolke et al., 2013). These consequences are particularly prominent in the context of the transition to college, where first-year students who have experienced bullying report higher levels of depression and anxiety than their peers (Bowes et al., 2015; Copeland et al., 2013). These findings indicate that bullying history can have enduring mental health and adjustment consequences during the college transition, necessitating closer attention to psychological mechanisms.

College students with a history of bullying can be considered as a vulnerable population in terms of mental health, and their emotions

have not been investigated thoroughly in the long-term, especially in the Indian context. Despite the fact that bullying within school environments has received some interest, its long-term implications on emerging adults who survive within a multicultural region like Kerala have been subjected to little empirical focus. This oversight is important, as the college years are a critical period of development characterized by identity formation, emotion regulation, and increased autonomy. The complexity of bullying experiences, mainly among subgroups like bully-victims, individuals who have both experienced and perpetrated bullying, requires a deeper understanding of the interaction between risk and resilience factors. In this context, the present review synthesizes evidence on psychological outcomes and adaptive behaviors among bullying-victims in colleges with bullying histories.

The current review paper includes the studies on long-term mental health outcomes of bullying victimization in childhood taken from electronic databases like PubMed, APA PsycArticles, ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Google Scholar, JSTOR, using a combination of key terms linked to childhood bullying victimization and long-term mental health outcomes. The searching strategy comprised a combination of keywords, including “bullying” OR “school bullying” OR “peer victimization” OR “victims of bullying” AND “childhood trauma” OR “mental health” OR “psychological distress” OR “self-esteem” OR “emotion regulation” OR “distress tolerance” OR “resilience” OR “forgiveness” OR “emerging adulthood” OR “college students”. The review is structured to include evidence on self-esteem, emotion regulation, distress tolerance, psychological distress, resilience, and forgiveness, and focuses on implications of the research on campus mental health systems within the Indian context. The next sections present a

Author Note

Navanitha M., Ph.D. Research Scholar, Department of Psychology Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
E-mail: navnithamadhav@gmail.com
Annalakshmi N., Professor & Head, Department of Psychology Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Annalakshmi N., Professor & Head, Department of Psychology Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu
E-mail: narayanan.annalakshmi@buc.edu.in

literature review of resources covering the long-term psychological and emotional impacts of childhood bullying and their persistence into adulthood.

Bullying History and Mental Health Outcomes

Victims are six times more likely to experience serious physical or psychiatric problems like depression, anxiety, obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD), and suicidal behaviour later in life (Hashorva et al., 2017). Additionally, in most cases, bullying leads to chronic emotional disturbances, which include social anxiety, recurrent sadness, shame, anger, vengeful thoughts, and post-traumatic stress disorder (deLara, 2018). Overt victimization was consistently linked to both externalizing issues and internalizing issues in adolescents (Annalakshmi & Deepak, 2021). Victims of bullying have lower mental health functioning, negative perceptions of well-being and more depression and anxiety symptoms, as well as worse physical health than non-bullied individuals (Holt et al., 2014). Mental health issues constitute one of the main reasons for college dropout, pointing to the larger academic and emotional burden of bullying (Gruttadaro & Crudo, 2012).

Bullying History and Self-esteem

Self-esteem is a crucial factor that determines how people socialize and become susceptible to bullying. Individuals with low self-esteem may get involved in bullying to assert power and increase self-esteem (Crocker & Luhtanen, 2003). A stable relationship exists between low self-esteem and both bullying perpetration and victimization in children and adolescents (Tsaousis, 2016). Victims showed less self-esteem and more depression and suicidal thoughts than bullies and uninvolved peers (Salmon et al., 1998). Positive school climate has the potential to reduce bullying, especially among students who have high esteem (Gendron et al., 2011). Students who become victims are more likely to skip classes and have a strong inverse relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement, as well as a positive association with depression (Eisenberg et al., 2003; Jamir et al., 2014). All these findings show that self-esteem functions as a determinant and a result of bullying behaviour, which has a significant impact on the emotional well-being of people and their academic involvement throughout childhood and adolescence.

Impact of bullying is further influenced by family and environmental factors. Parental overcontrol, neglect, and abuse are also reported to be higher in the victims, exposure to physical and sexual abuse and personal illness or disabilities are also more prevalent (Gladstone et al., 2006). Childhood trauma, like bullying, has a strong impact on the psychological development of a person throughout adolescence and adulthood, and is linked to various adult-related mental health problems, including post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), substance abuse, and physical health problems (Jiloha, 2018; Yehuda et al., 2001). It is important to study these effects on undergraduates because the development of social relationships and identity is a formative phase in emerging adulthood (Arnett, 2000). The findings highlight that the effects of bullying in the family, which is aggravated by negative childhood experiences, are severe on psychological development, mental health, and interpersonal functioning, especially at the crucial period of emerging adulthood. Although the self-esteem reviews suggest an intrapersonal vulnerability pathway, it alone is not an adequate

explanation of symptom persistence into adulthood. This indicates regulatory processes such as the generation, appraisal, and coping with emotions as the probable mechanisms that are likely to connect early victimization with subsequent distress.

Bullying History and Emotion Regulation

Emotion regulation is often one of the aspects at which victims of bullying struggle to manage, which makes them more prone to further psychological distress and victimization (Vacca et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2024). Exposed to bullying as a young adult has been attributed with the exposure of vulnerability to emotional, mental and social problems (Kim et al., 2011) because this is a period when an individual is learning the core emotion regulation skills. Timing and repetitive nature of bullying experience determine the extent of severity of long-term effects, which becomes maladaptive to emotional regulation patterns (Schäfer et al., 2004). These interferences can lead to persistent anxiety and inability to deal with negative emotions because victims usually internalize the trauma and cannot control the expression of their emotions (Esbensen & Carson, 2009). Victims frequently report lasting emotional distress that can extend well into adulthood and is worsened by other adverse childhood experiences (Miller et al., 2023). Regarding bullying, early interpersonal trauma can serve as a stressor interacting with the pre-existing emotional sensitivity to cause future difficulties in emotion regulation and distress tolerance. This is one of the reasons why some people become affected with persistent emotional problems after bullying, and other people show resilience based on their psychological and support networks.

The hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis gets chronically activated due to childhood adversity, such as bullying and can interfere with the development of healthy emotion regulation pathways (Pollak, 2015). The increased levels of cortisol and autonomic dysregulation, which are physiological indicators of poor emotion regulation in adulthood, were associated with the previous exposure of victimization and bystander experiences, and it was presumed that bullying had a permanent effect on neurobiological stress systems (Camodeca & Nava, 2022). Emotion regulation is, therefore, regarded as one of the key factors to understand the psychological impact of early trauma (Miu et al., 2022). These highlight the significance of the multifactorial approach to the study of the effects of bullying. Although emotion regulation is a key determinant of how individuals respond to early trauma, the effects it has on long-term outcomes can differ in individuals depending on their more global psychological and environmental context. A related, but different construct is the distress tolerance that embodies the ability to stay goal-oriented in states of high emotions and is perhaps the difference between dysregulated emotions escalating into avoidance, withdrawal or risk behaviour.

Bullying History and Distress Tolerance

Distress tolerance, the ability to endure psychological difficulties while pursuing goals or managing internal states, is an important psychological process that influences interpersonal and emotional functioning (Simons & Gaher, 2005). Individuals with low distress tolerance tend to see negative emotions as unbearable, which can result in avoidance behaviours, emotional suppression or other maladaptive coping mechanisms like rumination and withdrawal. Low distress tolerance would hinder conflict resolution and

emotional communication, which results in poor relationships and social isolation (Matheny et al., 2016). In trying to control distress, people can act impulsively or defensively in social circumstances, thus worsening interpersonal problems.

Bullying victims ruminating and having lower distress tolerance have higher chances of developing depressive symptoms during young adulthood (Labella et al., 2023). Under the circumstances that people have no capacity to tolerate distress, such thoughts may overwhelm them, making them emotionally exhausted and more susceptible to depression. Adaptive cognitive coping methods, including positive refocusing and cognitive reappraisal, on the other hand, have proven to mediate the psychological effects of bullying (Garnefski & Kraaij, 2014). Managing psychological discomfort through distress tolerance or adaptive coping is a critical factor in defining emotional outcomes and cultivating long-term resilience. The findings highlight the significance of supportive relationships as being now critical for the protective power against emotional damages of bullying. Accordingly, distress tolerance is closely tied to broader psychological distress outcomes among those who have a bullying history.

Bullying History and Psychological Distress

Bullying is a prolonged form of social stress, where there is repeated misuse of power through aggressive behaviour or deliberate harm caused by peers (Zarate-Garza et al., 2017). This stress does not only exist based on the occurrences of the past but also the anticipation of such events in the future, which adds to the psychological burden (Aluedse, 2006). Students at colleges who were bullied as children and believed they could do nothing to help themselves reported being depressed at much higher rates than those who believed that they could defend themselves (Oblath et al., 2019) which emphasizes the importance of perceived agency in psychological resilience. Increased dissociation, sleeping difficulties, suicidal ideation, and mental health impairment are all reported by the victims (Sesar, 2012; Valera-Pozo et al., 2021). The worst consequences of bullying are observed in victims and bully-victims, who have high levels of anxiety, depression, and chronic stress (Smokowski & Evans, 2019). The experiences of bullying alone are linked to psychosis-like symptoms among university students, independent of other variables, including childhood trauma and depression (Zhao et al., 2022), which demonstrates the wide range of psychological implications that may arise as a result of early victimization. The longitudinal studies also affirm that individuals who are bullied at the age of 7-11 have a higher chance of developing mental problems at the age of 23 (Takizawa et al., 2014). Bullying is also associated with childhood trauma, which leads to negative social experiences in college, and is mediated by internalizing issues like stress and depression (Jenkins et al., 2020). The findings highlight how social support, personal resilience, and self-efficacy play an important role in reducing the long-term damage of bullying. Although the past history of bullying increases the levels of psychological distress among college students, resilience is a factor that can lessen the negative impact and promote an adaptive outcome.

Bullying History and Resilience

Resilience is one of the factors that minimize the psychological effects of bullying and enables adolescents to have fewer negative

emotional consequences (Narayanan & Betts, 2014). In bullying victimization and emerging adulthood, resilience acts as an interactive process between individual agency and social resources within the environment (Lidberg et al., 2024). Adolescents who have high resilience tend to experience more favourable outcomes when facing challenges than those with lower resilience. Such persons get out of distressing experiences faster and more efficiently (Luthar et al., 2000). People with higher resilience tend to experience less negative impact from adverse events, mainly due to better coping mechanisms, emotion regulation skills, and availability of supportive relationships (Sapouna & Wolke, 2013). Instead of being a personality trait or a genetic trait, resilience is developed through repeated positive experiences as well as relationships with family members and other peer relationships, neighbours, and the community at large (Brooks, 2006; Rutter, 2006). Resilience is developed with the help of individual, family, and peer factors, which help to reduce depression and delinquency in adolescents who have been exposed to bullying (Sapouna & Wolke, 2013). Resilience is also one of the protective factors reducing the risk of targeting and protecting the emotional impact in case of victimization (Hinduja & Patchin, 2017).

High school bullying has a detrimental effect on motivation and transition adjustment to college, where the period requires autonomy, resilience, and social adaptability (Goodboy et al., 2015). Early bullying experiences may interfere with building social confidence and trust, making it challenging for victims to form meaningful peer relationships during their adulthood (Jantzer et al., 2006). Resilience is an important factor that determines how bullying victimization affects the development of depression in children (Zhou et al., 2016). The connection between bullying and self-efficacy in young men was mediated by resilience and thus indicated that resilient persons can still have a sense of competence and control in spite of having received repeated victimization (Narayanan & Betts, 2014). This is why some individuals maintain psychological stability even when exposed to adverse experiences. These results also indicate that resilience, which is influenced by individual factors and the social support system, can simplify the psychological effects of bullying to an extent. Extending the protective role of resilience in bullying long-term negative effects, forgiveness serves as a complementary process that protects mental health threats in victimized college students.

Bullying History and Forgiveness

Forgiveness emerges as a crucial element in the emotional recovery of the victims and the perpetrators and provides a pathway to psychological healing and behaviour transformation. To the victims, forgiveness may serve the purpose of getting rid of resentment, anger, and feelings of shame that persistently linger when victims experience bullying. Forgiveness is a solution through which individuals cope to have better mental and physical health because it enables them to get rid of negative emotions and restore the psychological balance (Baskin & Enright, 2004). This is especially useful where external support is not available and students manage with distress on their own and recapture the ability to have control of their emotional condition (Worthington & Scherer, 2004). People who have forgiven others are likely to have higher emotional regulation, reduced stress, and elevated satisfaction in life, which reduces the negative psychological damage that victims of bullying experience (Egan & Todorov, 2009).

Adolescents who have good self-control and forgiveness ability are less likely to indulge in bullying behaviours because they have the capacity of managing their emotions and lower impulsive behaviours (García-Vázquez et al., 2020). Students who demonstrate more prominent levels of such traits are less prone to bullying since they are better equipped to deal with interpersonal tensions and react to provocation in non-aggressive forms (Chen & Zhu, 2022; Sechi et al., 2023). This would assist individuals in getting over the experience of victimization to establish a positive relationship with each other; hence, forgiveness will be central in recovery and prevention. Forgiveness not only helps victims but also perpetrators by fostering mutual respect and emotional responsibility (Egan & Todorov, 2009). These findings point out that forgiveness is not only a moral or interpersonal process, but also a psychological coping process. Overall, the findings indicate that forgiveness is not only a personal coping process but also a transformative social process that nurtures resilience and promotes positive interpersonal functioning among students who are affected by bullying.

Research Gaps in Existing Literature and Future Directions

In India, the bullying studies are limited because of the large population of the country and the diverse socio-cultural setting (Milfont & Fischer, 2010; Smith et al., 2018). Although there are studies that have linked bullying with mental health issues, deeper research is needed to understand the psychological mechanisms that guide individuals to cope and adjust to these situations, especially among emerging adults, who are largely overlooked in existing literature. Most studies have focused on children and adolescents, leaving a gap about the long-term implications of college students who were bullied previously in their lives. There is a dearth of mixed-method retrospective studies in this field, even though it is important to discuss the impact of childhood bullying experiences on mental well-being in adulthood. This gap should be addressed to develop an effective intervention and support system aimed at promoting emotional recovery and social inclusion. While outcomes like depression, anxiety, and low self-esteem have been documented, very few studies have examined how these difficulties evolve or interact with individual coping mechanisms. Internal capacities like distress tolerance and emotion regulation are still under-researched and remain underexplored, and there is a lack of comprehensive frameworks that account for the complex interaction of psychological responses in this population. Based on this, the review illuminates such gaps and summarizes the existing knowledge on bullying experiences and psychological functioning in the context of emerging adulthood.

Conclusion

Bullying victimization is a serious psychosocial problem for college students worldwide. Similar to the adversity faced by marginalized communities, bullying creates a condition that threatens the fundamental needs of safety and a sense of belonging. The emotional distress of such a population is usually accompanied by the inability to control emotions and tolerate discomfort that provokes the development of coping strategies that rather intensify distress instead of alleviating it. Though some individuals exhibit strong emotional adjustment, others show lasting psychological difficulties, emphasizing the need to investigate the internal

processes that shape these varied outcomes. Such psychological reactions contribute to the explanation of why people similar in their experiences can take different approaches to recovery. The synthesis of the existing literature reflects several significant gaps such as the absence of longitudinal data of college students, limited cultural adaptation of mental health interventions, and the inquiry of the interaction of bullying features with psychological functioning. Through the cultural context of India, there is a need to enlighten more culturally sensitive support processes, and also understand better how early social trauma enters into our subsequent emotional health even in emerging adulthood.

References

- Aluede, O. (2006). Bullying in schools: A form of child abuse in schools. *Educational Research Quarterly*, 30(1), 37-49.
- Annalakshmi, N., & Deepak, K. (2021). Victimization, student-teacher relations and psychological problems among adolescents. *The Indian Journal of Social Work*, 82(1), 17-42. <https://doi.org/10.32444/ijsw.2021.82.1.17-42>
- Arnett, J. J. (2000). Emerging adulthood: A theory of development from the late teens through the twenties. *American Psychologist*, 55(5), 469-480. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.5.469>
- Baskin, T. W., & Enright, R. D. (2004). Intervention studies on forgiveness: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Counseling and Development*, 82(1), 79-90. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1556-6678.2004.tb00288.x>
- Bowes, L., Joinson, C., Wolke, D., & Lewis, G. (2015). Peer victimisation during adolescence and its impact on depression in early adulthood: Prospective cohort study in the United Kingdom. *BMJ*, 350(jun02 2), h2469. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.h2469>
- Brooks, J. E. (2006). Strengthening resilience in children and youths: Maximizing opportunities through the schools. *Children and Schools*, 28(2), 69-76. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cs/28.2.69>
- Camodeca, M., & Nava, E. (2022). The long-term effects of bullying, victimization, and bystander behavior on emotion regulation and its physiological correlates. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*, 37(3-4), NP2056-NP2075. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260520934438>
- Chen, Q., & Zhu, Y. (2022). The roles of gratitude and mindfulness between cyberbullying perpetration and depression among children in rural China: A moderated mediation model. *Health and Social Care in the Community*, 30(6), e5811-e5818. <https://doi.org/10.1111/hsc.14012>
- Copeland, W. E., Wolke, D., Angold, A., & Costello, E. J. (2013). Adult psychiatric outcomes of bullying and being bullied by peers in childhood and adolescence. *JAMA Psychiatry*, 70(4), 419. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapsychiatry.2013.504>
- Crocker, J., & Luhtanen, R. K. (2003). Level of self-esteem and contingencies of self-worth: Unique effects on academic, social, and financial problems in college students. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 29(6), 701-712. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0146167203029006003>
- deLara, E. W. (2018). Consequences of childhood bullying on mental health and relationships for young adults. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 28(9), 2379-2389. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-018-1197-y>
- Egan, L. A., & Todorov, N. (2009). Forgiveness as a coping strategy to allow school students to deal with the effects of being bullied: Theoretical and empirical discussion. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 28(2), 198-222. <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.2009.28.2.198>
- Eisenberg, M. E., Neumark-Sztainer, D., & Perry, C. L. (2003). Peer harassment, school connectedness, and academic achievement. *Journal of School Health*, 73(8), 311-316. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1746-1561.2003.tb06588.x>
- Esbensen, F.A., & Carson, D. C. (2009). Consequences of being bullied: Results from a longitudinal assessment of bullying victimization in a multisite sample of American students. *Youth and Society*, 41(2), 209-233. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X09351067>
- García-Vázquez, F. I., Valdés-Cuervo, A. A., & Parra-Pérez, L. G. (2020). The effects of forgiveness, gratitude, and self-control on reactive and proactive aggression in bullying. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(16), 5760. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17165760>
- Garnefski, N., & Kraaij, V. (2014). Bully victimization and emotional problems in adolescents: Moderation by specific cognitive coping strategies? *Journal of Adolescence*, 37(7), 1153-1160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2014.07.005>
- Gendron, B. P., Williams, K. R., & Guerra, N. G. (2011). An Analysis of bullying among students within schools: Estimating the effects of individual normative beliefs, Self-Esteem, and school climate. *Journal of School Violence*, 10(2), 150-164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15388220.2010.539166>
- Gladstone, G. L., Parker, G. B., & Malhi, G. S. (2006). Do bullied children become

- anxious and depressed adults? *The Journal of Nervous and Mental Disease*, 194(3), 201-208. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.nmd.0000202491.99719.c3>
- Goodboy, A. K., Martin, M. M., & Goldman, Z. W. (2015). Students' experiences of bullying in high school and their adjustment and motivation during the first semester of college. *Western Journal of Communication*, 80(1), 60-78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10570314.2015.1078494>
- Gruttadaro, D., & Crudo, D. (2012). *College students speak: A survey report on mental health*. National Alliance on Mental Illness.
- Hashorva, A., Pengili, T., Lici, M., & Prifti, I. (2017). What are the mental health impacts on adults coming from childhood bullying? *European Psychiatry*, 41(S1), S128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2017.01.1942>
- Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2017). Cultivating youth resilience to prevent bullying and cyberbullying victimization. *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 73, 51-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2017.09.010>
- Holt, M. K., Green, J. G., Reid, G., DiMeo, A., Espelage, D. L., Felix, E. D., Furlong, M. J., Poteat, V. P., & Sharkey, J. D. (2014). Associations between past bullying experiences and psychosocial and academic functioning among college students. *Journal of American College Health*, 62(8), 552-560. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2014.947990>
- Jamir, T., Devi, N. P., Lenin, R. K., Roshan, L., & Sameeta, N. G. (2014). The relationship between bullying victimization, self-esteem, and depression among school-going adolescents. *International Journal of Management and Social Science*, 2(12), 477-486. ISSN: 2321-1784.
- Jantzer, A. M., Hoover, J. H., & Narloch, R. (2006). The relationship between School-Aged Bullying and Trust, shyness and quality of friendships in young adulthood. *School Psychology International*, 27(2), 146-156. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034306064546>
- Jenkins, L., McNeal, T., Drayer, J., & Wang, Q. (2020). Childhood trauma history and negative social experiences in college. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Trauma*, 14(1), 103-113. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-020-00315-z>
- Jiloha, R. (2018). Childhood bully victims: Their future mental health. *Journal of Indian Association for Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 14(1), 19-30. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0973134220180104>
- Kim, M. J., Catalano, R. F., Haggerty, K. P., & Abbott, R. D. (2011). Bullying at elementary school and problem behaviour in young adulthood: A study of bullying, violence and substance use from age 11 to age 21. *Criminal Behaviour and Mental Health*, 21(2), 136-144. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cbm.804>
- Labella, M. H., Klein, N. D., Yeboah, G., Bailey, C., Doane, A. N., Kaminer, D., & Bravo, A. J. (2023). Childhood bullying victimization, emotion regulation, rumination, distress tolerance, and depressive symptoms: A cross-national examination among young adults in seven countries. *Aggressive Behavior*, 50(1), e22111. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ab.22111>
- Lidberg, J., Berne, S., & Frisén, A. (2024). From childhood bullying victimization to resilience in emerging adulthood. *Scandinavian Journal of Psychology*, 65(3), 521-532. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sjop.12999>
- Luthar, S. S., Cicchetti, D., & Becker, B. (2000). The Construct of Resilience: a critical evaluation and guidelines for future work. *Child Development*, 71(3), 543-562. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00164>
- Matheny, N. L., Smith, H. L., Summers, B. J., McDermott, K. A., Macatee, R. J., & Cogle, J. R. (2016). The role of distress tolerance in multiple facets of hostility and willingness to forgive. *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 41(2), 170-177. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-016-9808-7>
- Milfont, T. L., & Fischer, R. (2010). Testing measurement invariance across groups: applications in cross-cultural research. *International Journal of Psychological Research*, 3, 111-130. <https://doi.org/10.21500/20112084.857>
- Miller, H. H., Jenkins, L., Putzeys, S., Kaminski, S., & Woodall, M. (2023). Bullying victimization and adverse childhood experiences: Retrospective reports of relative impact on emotional distress. *Journal of Child and Adolescent Trauma*, 17(2), 481-493. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40653-023-00567-5>
- Miu, A. C., Szentágotai-Tátar, A., Balázs, R., Nechita, D., Bunea, I., & Pollak, S. D. (2022). Emotion regulation as mediator between childhood adversity and psychopathology: A meta-analysis. *Clinical Psychology Review*, 93, 102141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2022.102141>
- Narayanan, A., & Betts, L. R. (2014). Bullying behaviors and victimization experiences among adolescent students: The role of resilience. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 175(2), 134-146. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221325.2013.834290>
- Oblath, R., Green, J. G., Guzmán, J., Felix, E. D., Furlong, M. J., Holt, M., & Sharkey, J. (2019). Retrospective perceptions of power imbalance in childhood bullying among college students. *Journal of American College Health*, 68(8), 891-899. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07448481.2019.1633334>
- Olweus, D. (1993). *Bullying at school: What we know and what we can do* (Understanding Children's Worlds). Oxford: Blackwell Publishing.
- Olweus, D. (2013). School bullying: development and some important challenges. *Annual Review of Clinical Psychology*, 9(1), 751-780. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-clinpsy-050212-185516>
- Pollak, S. D. (2015). Developmental psychopathology: recent advances and future challenges. *World Psychiatry*, 14(3), 262-269. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wps.20237>
- Rutter, M. (2006). Implications of resilience Concepts for scientific understanding. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 1094(1), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1196/annals.1376.002>
- Salmon, G., James, A., & Smith, D. M. (1998). Bullying in schools: Self reported anxiety, depression, and self-esteem in secondary school children. *BMJ*, 317(7163), 924-925. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.317.7163.924>
- Sapouna, M., & Wolke, D. (2013). Resilience to bullying victimization: The role of individual, family and peer characteristics. *Child Abuse and Neglect*, 37(11), 997-1006. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chiabu.2013.05.009>
- Schäfer, M., Korn, S., Smith, P. K., Hunter, S. C., Mora-Merchán, J. A., Singer, M. M., & Van Der Meulen, K. (2004). Lonely in the crowd: Recollections of bullying. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 22(3), 379-394. <https://doi.org/10.1348/0261510041552756>
- Sechi, C., Cabras, C., & Sideli, L. (2023). Cyber-victimisation and cyber-bullying: The mediation role of the dispositional forgiveness in female and male adolescents. *Journal of Beliefs and Values*, 45(4), 488-502. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13617672.2023.2180722>
- Sesar, K. (2012). The relationship between difficulties in psychological adjustment in young adulthood and exposure to bullying behaviour in childhood and adolescence. *Acta Medica Academica*, 41(2), 131-144. <https://doi.org/10.5644/ama2006-124.46>
- Simons, J. S., & Gaher, R. M. (2005). The distress tolerance scale: Development and validation of a self-report measure. *Motivation and Emotion*, 29(2), 83-102. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11031-005-7955-3>
- Smith, P. K., Sundaram, S., Spears, B. A., Blaya, C., Schäfer, M., & Sandhu, D. (Eds.) (2018). *Bullying, cyberbullying and student well-being in schools: Comparing European, Australian and Indian perspectives*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Smokowski, P. R., & Evans, C. B. R. (2019). Consequences of bullying in childhood, adolescence, and adulthood: An ecological perspective. *Bullying and victimization across the lifespan* (pp. 59-69). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-20293-4_3
- Takizawa, R., Maughan, B., & Arseneault, L. (2014). Adult health outcomes of childhood bullying victimization: Evidence from a five-decade longitudinal british birth cohort. *American Journal of Psychiatry*, 171(7), 777-784. <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.ajp.2014.13101401>
- Tsaousis, I. (2016). The relationship of self-esteem to bullying perpetration and peer victimization among schoolchildren and adolescents: A meta-analytic review. *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, 31, 186-199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2016.09.005>
- Vacca, M., Cerolini, S., Zegretti, A., Zagaria, A., & Lombardo, C. (2023). Bullying victimization and adolescent depression, anxiety and stress: The mediation of cognitive emotion regulation. *Children*, 10(12), 1897. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10121897>
- Valera-Pozo, M., Flexas, A., Servera, M., Aguilar-Mediavilla, E., & Adrover-Roig, D. (2021). Long-term profiles of bullying victims and aggressors: A retrospective study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.631276>
- Wang, Y., Wang, T., Wang, J., Zeng, L., Li, G., Li, J., Zhou, Y., & Wang, Y. (2024). The school bullying victimization in adolescents with non-suicidal self-injury: The role of coping strategies and emotion regulation. *Stress and Health*, 40(6), e3506. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smi.3506>
- Wolke, D., Copeland, W. E., Angold, A., & Costello, E. J. (2013). Impact of bullying in childhood on adult health, wealth, crime, and social outcomes. *Psychological Science*, 24(10), 1958-1970. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0956797613481608>
- Worthington, E. L., & Scherer, M. (2004). Forgiveness is an emotion-focused coping strategy that can reduce health risks and promote health resilience: Theory, review, and hypotheses. *Psychology and Health*, 19(3), 385-405. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0887044042000196674>
- Yehuda, R., Spertus, I. L., & Golier, J. A. (2001). *Chapter 5. Relationship between childhood traumatic experiences and PTSD in adults*. In American Psychiatric Association Publishing eBooks (pp. 117-158). <https://doi.org/10.1176/appi.books.9781615377046.lg05>
- Zarate-Garza, P. P., Biggs, B. K., Croarkin, P., Morath, B., Leffler, J., Cuellar-Barboza, A., & Tye, S. J. (2017). How well do we understand the Long-Term health implications of childhood bullying? *Harvard Review of Psychiatry*, 25(2), 89-95. <https://doi.org/10.1097/hrp.0000000000000137>
- Zhao, J., Lu, X., Liu, Y., Wang, N., Chen, D., Lin, I., Li, X., Zhou, F., & Wang, C. (2022). The unique contribution of past bullying experiences to the presence of Psychosis-Like experiences in university students. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.839630>
- Zhou, Z., Liu, Q., Niu, G., Sun, X., & Fan, C. (2016). Bullying victimization and depression in Chinese children: A moderated mediation model of resilience and mindfulness. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 104, 137-142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2016.07.040>

Received January 7, 2026

Revision received February 10, 2026

Accepted February 13, 2026